

ISSN No: 3433-7133
emeraldpublishinggroup.com

892 Berne St SE, Atlanta, GA 30316, United States

Abstra International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research

Volume 13 Issue 2, August 2024

46

IMPACT OF BANDITRY ON TRANS-BORDER SECURITY IN NIGERIA, 2010-2021

^[1] Jacob Angel Emobweseh and ^[2] Dantani Agabi Yakubu

^[1] Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University Keffi, Nigeria

^[2] Department of Political Science and International Relations, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study examines the impact of banditry on Trans-border security in Nigeria with a focus on the Nigeria-Niger border at Jibia in Katsina State. The main objective of the research is to examine the role banditry has played in causing threat to Nigeria's border security from 2010-2021. The study adopted both primary and secondary methods of data collection to investigate the problem. The theoretical framework adopted is the State Fragility Theory. The study found that the nature of banditry has assumed a dangerous trend and this has made victims of banditry not to even know where to access help and get protected. The study finds out that the nature of banditry is such that the victims experience threats from bandit. People are vulnerable due to economic hardship and the poor background they came from. Moreso, issues that are particular to Nigerian banditry in its relations with other countries is causing a bad image for Nigeria. For example, updated guidance for prosecutors on victims of trafficking produced by the Crown Prosecution Service (CPS) in London on May 2021, recommended that protection for the victims of banditry must be structured in such a way that victims can and will access it. The study concluded that banditry is a structural and collective attack against humanity which has assumed a dangerous trend, having its roots from the colonial times. The study recommended that the Federal Government should enact Laws that will pronounce stiffer jail terms for culprit of banditry. There should be a call for a review of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Resident Permit to checkmate the influx and activities of bandit. Effective sustenance of joint patrol operations existing at the country's various borders to match with the increasing rate of Trans-border crimes. Banditry in Nigeria is due to population boom and unfavourable economic conditions that aggravate unemployment, under-employment and insecurity which prompt citizens to emigrate in search of opportunities such as education, decent jobs and higher income. Banditry remains a major challenge to the global community because it is a threat to human race and one of the major causes of crimes around the world at large.

How to Cite this Paper:

Jacob Angel Emobweseh & Dantani Agabi Yakubu (2024) Impact of Banditry on Trans-Border Security in Nigeria, 2010-2021, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol. 13(2) pp.046

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13788417>

Corresponding Author

kaigamajacob@yahoo.com

Keywords

Impact, Banditry, Security, Primary Data, Secondary Data

INTRODUCTION

One of the vexatious issues that have characterized Nigeria's political, economic and other landscape are cross-order crimes which are common among countries with porous borders. In Nigeria most of the state that worst hit by the menace of banditry in Nigeria started feeling the impact of this trans-border crime around 2010 when there were

reported cases of large-scale cattle theft and some elements of injuries inflicted on pastoral communities in the course of the rustling by the bandits (Rufai, 2017). Earlier, only the border communities were mostly affected, while the remaining part of the country was still battling with the challenges of animal theft. Comparatively, first major incidence of cattle rustling in the Tahoua region, according to Muhammadu (2017) was reported in northern part of Tahour around 2010 which is one of the main pastoralist zones in Niger Republic. As further revealed by Muhammadu (2017), some unknown armed men during the period were said to have rustled about 145 heads of cattle around Azawak and Chinta- Barade. The incidence became an issue of great concern to the then authority of the regions, while Northern Nigeria side, the menace was gradually gaining grounds as bandits and rustlers were busy forming criminal gangs as well as devising means to intensify their activities (Rufai, 2017).

Thus, Police Report (2011) asserts that some Touareg and Fulani from Niger Republic formed part of the early bandits that established criminal gangs in Nigeria. Jimi (2011) clarified that membership of said gangs received training around Birnin Gwari and Dansadau forests which is very large but extended thickest that cut across the States of Kaduna, Niger, Katsina, Kebbi, Zamfara and Sokoto down to some parts of Niger Republic. Some of the animals rustled in the early period were either sold or kept in this forest zone. As argued by Okoli (2017), proceeds from banditry were partly used in the procurement of Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALW) for further perpetration of insecurity in the regions. There was constant interception of illegal SALW movements across the borderlands. Therefore, new business emerged when some people along the border areas suddenly became gun-runners at the expense of the communities' peace and made a lot of money from it. A typical example was Rabeh, who had since been serving a jail term in Tahoua prison for the supply of arms to the bandits in both Nigeria and Niger Republic (Police Report, 2017). The pervasive banditry and its associated threats to security, which have enveloped the country, particularly, Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Sokoto and Niger States, have become a worrisome national security issue of public concern (Olaniyan & Yahaya, 2016). Reports indicate the flourishing of bandit groups, whose members were seen displaying automatic weapons, terrorizing herder settlements, farms, villages and the highways with the mission of killing people, kidnapping and pillaging cows (Olaniyan, 2018). It was reported that between October, 2013 and March, 2014, 7,000 cattle were rustled from commercial livestock farms and traditional herders in Northern Nigeria (Bashir, 2014; Tauna, 2016) while about 330 attacks were made by bandits and 1,460 deaths were recorded between January and July, 2019 (Abdullahi, 2019). In most cases, the bandits killed and maimed the people and raped the women before dispossessing them of their cows (Akowe & Kayode, 2014) while in some instances, they also kidnapped girls or women in the process (Adeniyi, 2015; Yusuf, 2015).

Suffice to say that Katsina, Kaduna, Zamfara, Sokoto, Kebbi and Niger have been mostly affected by the scourge of banditry. Of these six states, Kaduna, Katsina, Zamfara and Niger have been the most critical hot spots. It is however, pertinent to note that the incidences of banditry are not limited to the six states mentioned above. In fact, it is also prevalent in some parts of north-central region, in states like Nasarawa, Benue and Plateau which are equally regarded as hotbeds (Kuna & Jibrin 2016). Scholars like Gaye (2018), Olaniyan and Yahaya (2016), Suleiman (2017) and Mustapha (2019) have advanced several factors for the cause and prevalence of banditry in Nigeria. Some of the factors they argued include the fragility of Nigerian state, weak state institutions, especially the security agencies, availability of grossly ungoverned spaces, porosity of Nigeria's borders with its

neighboring countries and arms proliferation, weak leadership, corruption, unemployment and mass poverty. Furthermore, despite the federal framework adopted by Nigeria's forefathers, Nigeria's security architecture since the incursion of the military in Nigeria's politics is contrived in such a manner that the control of every security outfit is placed in the hands of the President at the centre. Though the governor is recognized by Nigeria's Constitution as the Chief Security Officer of the state, in actual fact, he wields no power over the police that could be put to use in times of crisis. This precarious situation places every governor at the mercy of the President in the period of crisis at the state level denying him the opportunity to confront security challenges with expediency and expertise. This is one of the reasons why people are clamoring for restructuring that will, among others, effect the creation of state police to meet the immediate needs of every state.

Statement of the Problem

There is no gainsaying the fact that banditry poses a serious challenge not only to the security of the affected states but to the country at large in view of its ever-increasing impacts and implications. The level at which armed bandits operate within the affected states calls for attention by both the State and Federal governments, more especially, since the latter controls the state security apparatuses. This complex situation of social violence and insecurity in the affected states had been on for almost a decade now (Okoli & Ogayi, 2018). The increasing attacks of bandit groups have led to the destruction of lives and properties, displacement of people from their communities; and a growing number of widows; widowers and orphans, who now reside in Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camps following the continued attacks of armed bandits on both farming and pastoral communities across different areas of the states (Okoli & Ochim, 2016; Mustapha, 2019).

Though the police is traditionally responsible for the maintenance of peace, law and order within the nation, it appears that its personnel are being overstretched by the responsibility of securing the political process and political functionaries of the state apart from the fact that it is ill-equipped to meet the challenges of contemporary security needs. In addition, Nigeria is under-policed, its personnel is grossly inadequate, running short of the United Nations requirements or ratio of one police to four hundred citizens. Furthermore, the salary of the police personnel is poor; welfare services are non-existent while there has been no incentive to boost their morale. The general social discontent and distrust among citizens have made the probable collaboration between the security men and the people fragile thus inhibiting the efficient and effective performance of security agencies in successfully confronting the bandit groups. This development has therefore, affected government efforts in achieving the desired goal of crushing banditry in the Northwest region.

Against the backdrop of the upsurge in incidences of banditry in recent times, this research examines the phenomenon of banditry as a trans-border crime as it affects the security of Nigeria in the fourth republic.

Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. To what extent have banditry impacted on security at the Nigeria-Niger border in Jibia?
- ii. What are the security measures been put in place to mitigate the impact of banditry in Jibia town?

- iii. How effective have these security measures been in combating crime at the Nigeria-Niger border in Jibia?
- iv. What are the challenges faced by Nigeria in implementing these security measures at the Nigeria-Niger border in Jibia border?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the impact of banditry on trans-border security in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives are:

- i. Analyze the security measures that have been put in place as a result of banditry in Jibia border.
- ii. Assess the effectiveness of the security measures been put in place in combating crime in Jibia border.
- iii. Evaluate the challenges faced by Nigeria in implementing security measures at Jibia border

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

The historical-descriptive research design was employed in this study. This involves a descriptive-analytical and narrative approach. Generally, historical research involves investigation, recording, analysis and interpretation of facts leading to the reconstruction of the past (Gberevbie, 2008; Alagoa, 1985). Data were sourced from historical documents that help in the critical analyses of the issue under investigation at the same time throw more light not only on the theoretical aspect of the research problem, but also on empirical evidences.

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Population of the Study

For this study, the sample of the population of the study covers respondents drawn from State Security Service, Nigeria Police, (FCT Command), Nigeria Customs Service- Abuja, Nigeria Immigration Service Abuja, Ministry of Interior and Ministry of Defense. These set of people will be used as the total population of the study and the various demographic characteristics of the population. The total population of the study is fifty-three thousand, two hundred and twenty-seven (53,227).

Table 1: Population and Sample Size of Institutions of Study using the Smith Formula

Institution	Population	Sample
State Security Service	138	21
Nigeria Police (Border Control Unit)	210	31
Nigeria Custom Service-NCS	512	77
Nigeria Immigration Service-NIS	602	90
Ministry of Interior	979	147
Ministry of Defence	227	34
Total	2668	400

Source: Field Survey, February 2022

Sample Size

Using the Smith (1984) formula, the sample size of this study comprises of 400 respondents comprising the staff of Nigeria Immigration Service, State Security Services, Nigeria police (Border Control Units), Nigeria customs service, Ministry of Interior and Ministry of Defense. In order to effectively determine the sampling representative of the entire population of the institutions viz-a-viz staff of the State Security Service, Nigerian Police, (Border Control

Units), Nigeria Immigration Service, Nigeria Customs Service Abuja, Ministry of Interior and Ministry of Defense (2668), the sample size for the study was determined scientifically using the formula by Smith (1984) below to calculate the sample size:

Margin of error is = 0.05 (5%) Where:

N = Population size which is the sum total of the numbers of institutions totalling = 2,668
3 = Constant

e = Margin of error (5%)

$$n = \frac{N}{3 + Ne^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2668}{3 + 2668 (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2668}{2671 \times 0}$$

$$n = \frac{2668}{6.6775} = 399 \text{ (Sample Size approximated to 400 participants) Sample size=400}$$

It is worth noting that questionnaires were shared to four hundred respondents, which is the sample size of this study. Out of the 400 respondents, 10 key players were interviewed to get first-hand information from the field. To assign the sample size of 400 to the different categories of respondents, the Bourley’s proportional allocation formula was adopted.

$$nb = \frac{n(n)}{N}$$

Where, P = Population, for instance; n = total sample size; N = population of the study.

The determination of each of the sample group given in the Table below:

Table 2: Determination of Sample Groups

Institution	Determination of Sample Group
State Security Service:	$\frac{138 \times 400}{2,668} = 21$
Nigeria, Police (Border Control Units):	$\frac{210 \times 400}{2,668} = 31$
Nigeria Custom Service –NCS:	$\frac{512 \times 400}{2,668} = 77$
Nigeria Immigration Service-NIS:	$\frac{602 \times 400}{2,668} = 90$
Ministry of Interior:	$\frac{979 \times 400}{2,668} = 147$
Ministry of Defense:	$\frac{227 \times 400}{2,668} = 34$

Sampling Technique

In the study, the non-probability or purposive sampling technique was adopted. Purposive sampling according to Garuba (2003) is a sampling technique that helps the researcher to use his or her discretion and judgement in identifying the population to be

studied. It is based on the conviction that the population that the researcher identified would give the accurate data that was used for this research. The selection of the population is done purposively. As such, since the research is qualitative, the researcher hopes to get documented data from the study population for analysis. In addition, the researcher purposively determines those that were approached for the needed data.

Method of Data Collection

The study relies on primary and secondary sources of data collection.

Primary Data

Questionnaires and Interviews were used for the purpose of this study. The primary method of data collection is the questionnaires and interview method. This method helps the researcher in getting required information from only qualified and persons working directly with the concern department/unit.

- **Questionnaire:** The choice of questionnaire is based on its suitability for generating comparable and quantifiable data covering a wider population within a short period. In support of this approach, [Surridge \(2002\)](#) submits that despite its weaknesses, quantitative data is particularly good at identifying commonalities amongst individuals and at characterizing the social positions occupied by individuals. The questionnaire consists of two sections in accordance with the objectives of the study. Questionnaires were distributed to respondents and were later collected for analysis. The questionnaire was an open ended using the Likert scale of Agree, Strongly Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree and Undecided. Here, the questionnaire was administered to a smaller number of respondents who are stakeholders in the area under study.
- **Interview:** Interview is a research method that gives the researcher some level of freedom of conversation on the topic been researched to discover an in-depth view of the respondents and the various circumstances associated with the topic. Interviews are quite helpful when detailed information is required; it is an excellent tool that affords the interviewer into context necessary for data as it offers more insight ([Boyce and Neale, 2006](#)). The flavour of oral evidence by respondents substantially will be used to consolidate the materials gathered from other sources such as documented evidence, questionnaire and other materials. On the other hand, interview method of data collection is not flawless; there are limitations for the interview research technique as it is prone to bias, time-consuming to interview, transcribe and analyze the data ([Boyce and Neale. 2006](#)).

Thus, by using this technique, the researcher will be able to gather relevant information about the introduction of these methods into the socio-economic demography of the conflict in the respective communities. In addition, interviews will be conducted with the various stakeholders on what should be done in terms of reviewing the existing management methods with a view to making them more effective and applicable in the state, to curb re-occurrence of such conflicts. Pictures of selected interviewees were taken and their voices were recorded for onward transcription and empirical analysis.

The study was supplemented with data sourced through some expert interviews with selected people involved in the focused institutions for the study. Interviews was conducted with selected members of the diplomatic corps, including career ambassadors of neighboring countries, immigrations and customs personnel, members of the security and intelligence services especially the military and the SSS as well as heads of agencies and parastatals all based in Abuja, Nigeria's capital. However, the use of interview gives us the opportunity of receiving direct information from our sample population.

Secondary Data

Secondary data collection involves intense library research and internet browsing. The implication for the study is that ample library search to collect and processed data has been undertaken. Books and journal articles, unpublished theses, government publications, and all other processed data collected have been able to complement, validate, or reject certain claims in primary data and other literature.

Historical or documentary sources of data collection were relied upon; data collection were sourced from text books, journals, monographs, newspapers and news magazines, published gazettes, unpublished theses and research projects. Documented data was also utilized from the study population for analysis. The internet has also been maximized with online resources including journal and book articles that are accessible providing important data on the subject matter.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Method of Data Analysis

The method of data analysis used for this study was simple percentage and cross tabulation tables as a platform to present and analyze the data collected from the field on the subject matter. Descriptive statistics were also used to describe the basic features of the data in a study. This provided simple summaries about the sample and the measures.

Data Presentation

Table 3: Number of Questionnaire Distributed and Returned

Institution	Distributed	Returned	Not returned
State Security Service (SSS)	21	19	2
Nigeria Police (Border Control Unit)	31	29	2
Nigeria Customs Service	77	69	8
Nigeria Immigration Service	90	78	12
Ministry of Interior	147	119	28
Ministry of Defense	34	31	3
Total	400	350	50

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 3 explains that twenty-one (21) questionnaires were distributed to the state security service, nineteen (19) retrieved while two (2) were not retrieved. About thirty-one (31) questionnaire were also distributed to the Nigerian Police (Border control unit), twenty-nine (29) retrieved, two (2) not retrieved.

Similarly, seventy-seven (77) questionnaires were also distributed to the Nigeria Custom Service, sixty-nine (69) retrieved, eight pending. On the other hand, out of the ninety (90) questionnaires distributed to the Nigeria Immigration Service, seventy-eight (78) were retrieved while twelve (12) were not retrieved. More also, one hundred and forty-seven (147) questionnaires were distributed to the Ministry of Interior, one hundred and nineteen (119) retrieved while twenty-eight (28) were not retrieved. Thirty-four (34) questionnaires were also distributed to the Ministry of Defense, thirty- one (31) retrieved, three (3) were not retrieved.

Table 4: Sex of the Respondents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Male	201	57.4%
Female	149	42.6%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 4 indicates that male gender constitutes the highest respondents with two hundred and one representing fifty-seven-point four percent (57.4%), while female respondents account for forty-two-point six percent (42.6) or one hundred and forty- nine. From the gender of the respondents, it can be deduced that the male gender is higher in number because more men are deployed to these offices. This is because of the sensitivity and hazards of the tasks involved, the men are therefore considered more capable of withstanding these hazards.

Table 5: Age of Respondents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
20-30	80	22.9%
31-40	160	45.7%
41-50	92	26.3%
51 & Above	18	5.1%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 5 shows that respondents between the ages of thirty-one and forty (31 & 40) constitute the highest number of respondents with total number of one hundred and sixty accounting for forty-five-point seven percent (45.7%), respondents between the ages of forty-one and fifty (41&50) is the second highest with a total number of ninety- two (92) accounting for twenty-six-point three percent (26.3%). Respondents between the ages of twenty and thirty (20 & account for eighty (80) or twenty-two-point nine percent (22.9%), while respondents between the ages of fifty and above (50+) are eighteen (18) representing five-point one percent (5.1%). The age bracket of 31-40 of the respondents is more because in most of the institutions visited by the researcher, the people deployed to these offices are within this age bracket. This is because they are considered computer savvy, which means they are more knowledgeable in the area of ICT and modern technology.

Table 6: Qualification of the Respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
B.sc	237	67.7%
M.Sc.	107	30.6%
PhD	6	1.7%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 6 indicates that respondents with B.Sc. constituted the majority of respondents. The above data shows that majority of the diplomats, civil and public servants who supplied the researcher with data relating to the impact of banditry on Nigeria's international image have the B.Sc. Qualification and represent sixty-seven-point seven (67.7%) percent which is the highest in the qualification of those sampled. The respondents with M.Sc. have the second highest with a thirty-point six percent (30.6%). Table 3.5 is the analysis of the respondents as well as the data supplied through the questionnaire distributed to the respondents sampled while those with PHD and above account for one point seven percent (1.7%). From the qualification of the respondents, it can be deduced that the respondents with B.SC qualification are more in number. This is because B.Sc. is the entry qualification requirement for staff in most of these institutions and grade level.

Results

This section analyses the results to the research questions utilizing data collected from the field and the objective is to arrive at realistic suggestions and recommendations.

Research Question 1: *To what extent have banditry impacted on security at the Nigeria-Niger border in Jibia?*

Table 7: Impact of Banditry on Trans-Border Security

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	136	38.9%
Disagree	11	3.1%
Strongly Agree	168	48%
Strongly Disagree	10	2.9%
Undecided	25	7.1%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Analyzing the responses of the respondents on the question the impact of banditry on Nigeria's national security, the above data showed that one hundred and sixty-eight (168) or forty-eight percent (48%) strongly agreed while one hundred and thirty-six (136) respondents accounting for thirty-eight-point nine percent (38.9 %) agreed. Respondents who disagree stood at eleven (11) or three-point one percent (3.1%) and those who strongly disagree accounts for two-point nine percent (2.9%) or ten (10). Twenty-five respondents (25) accounting for seven-point one percent (7.1%) were undecided. It is therefore safe to conclude that banditry affects Nigeria's Trans-Border Security in Nigeria.

Table 8: The Role of Bandits in Denting the External Image of Nigeria

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	238	68%
Disagree	11	3.1%
Strongly Agree	80	22.9%
Strongly Disagree	4	1.1%
Undecided	17	4.9%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 8 indicates that respondents are of the opinion that bandits have contributed seriously in denting the external image of Nigeria. This is because respondents who agree and those who strongly agree are in the majority, representing two hundred and thirty-eight (238) or sixty-eight percent (68%) and eighty representing twenty-two-point nine percent (22.9%) respectively. Seventeen respondents (17) representing four-point nine percent (4.9%) are undecided, eleven- or three-point one percent (3.1%) disagree and four respondents, representing one point one percent (1.1%) are strongly disagreed.

Research Question 2: *What are the security measures been put in place to mitigate the impact of banditry in Jibia town?*

Table 9: The Role of Nigeria Police Force in Trans-Border Security in Nigeria

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	215	61.4%
Disagree	19	5.4%
Strongly Agree	83	23.7%
Strongly Disagree	5	1.4%
Undecided	28	8%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 9 addresses the role of Nigeria Police Force in curbing insecurity in Nigeria. Data obtained from sample respondents shows that two hundred and fifteen (215) respondents or sixty-one-point one percent (61.1%) agree, while eighty-three (83) or twenty-three point seven (23.7%) were in strong agreement. Five-point four percent (5.4%) or 19 respondents disagree, one point four percent (1.4%) or five respondents strongly disagree while eight percent (8%) or

twenty-eight (28) were undecided. From the analysis of the data supplied by the sample respondents, it is clear that Nigeria Police Force has a huge role to play in curbing insecurity in Nigeria.

Table 10: Security Institutions and Banditry in Nigeria

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	165	47.1%
Disagree	18	5.1%
Strongly Agree	176	50.3%
Strongly Disagree	15	4.3%
Undecided	12	3.4%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Similarly, majority of the respondents agree to the question that the various security institutions in the country have assisted in the ensuring that the country and the society put a stop to banditry in Nigeria. In numerical terms, respondents who agree account for one hundred and sixty-five (165) or forty-seven-point one percent (47.1%) and those who strongly agree stood at one hundred and seventy-six (176) or fifty-point three percent (50.3%). On the other hand, those who disagree and strongly disagree are tied at two (2) or zero-point six percent (0.6%) each while five respondents (5) accounting for one point four percent (1.4%) were undecided.

Table 11: Religious Institutions and the Campaign against Banditry

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	204	58.3%
Disagree	10	2.9%
Strongly Agree	119	34%
Strongly Disagree	5	1.4%
Undecided	12	3.4%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

For the question on whether religious institutions have been used as tools of campaign against banditry in Nigeria, one hundred and nineteen respondents (119) or thirty-four percent (34%) strongly agree, while two hundred and four (204) respondents or fifty-eight points three percent (58.3%) agree. Twelve (12) or three-point four percent (3.4%) are undecided, ten (10) representing two-point nine percent (2.9%) disagree while five respondents (5) accounting for one point four percent (1.4%) strongly disagree. It is evident from the data analysis that religious institutions have been used as veritable tools of campaign against banditry in Nigeria.

Table 12: Traditional Institutions and Banditry in Nigeria

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	153	43.7%
Disagree	19	5.4%
Strongly Agree	157	44.9%
Strongly Disagree	19	5.4%
Undecided	13	3.7%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 4.15 addresses the issue of the use of traditional institutions as strategy to curb banditry in Nigeria. Respondents who agree account for one hundred and fifty-four (153) or forty-three-point seven percent (43.7%) while those who strongly agree stood at one hundred

and fifty-seven (157) or forty-four-point nine percent (44.9%). Those who strongly disagree stood at eight (8) or three-point seven percent (3.7%), those who disagreed recorded ten (10), representing two-point nine percent (2.9%), while those undecided stood at twenty-two (22) or six-point three percent (6.3%).

Research Question 3: *How effective have these security measures been in combating crime at the Nigeria-Niger border in Jibia?*

The strategies adopted by government to curb banditry in Nigeria are inadequate. This is due to government's inability to tackle some deep lying issues plaguing the country as expressed by respondents in the tables below:

Table 13: Illegal Migration of Persons

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	151	43.1%
Disagree	15	4.3%
Strongly Agree	158	45.1%
Strongly Disagree	6	1.7%
Undecided	20	5.7%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

On the question on whether illegal migration of persons have adversely affected Trans-border security in Nigeria. This is because respondents who agree and strongly agree were in the majority, representing one hundred and fifty-one (151) accounting for forty-three-point one percent (43.1%) and one hundred and fifty-eight representing forty-five-point one percent (45.1%) respectively. This is against the twenty (20) or five-point seven percent (5.7%), fifteen accounting for four-point three percent (4.3%) and six (6) or one point seven percent (1.7%) of those who are undecided, disagree and strongly disagree respondents.

Table 14: Poverty

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	134	38.3%
Disagree	2	0.6%
Strongly Agree	204	58.3%
Strongly Disagree	16	4.6%
Undecided	14	4%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

On the view that poverty has an intricate relationship with banditry/kidnapping, respondents who agree and strongly agree are in the majority having recorded the highest numbers of one hundred and thirty-four (134) or thirty-eight-point three percent (38.3%) and two hundred and four (204) or fifty-eight-point three percent (58.3%). Those who disagree are two (2) or zero-point six percent (0.6%), one (1) or zero-point three percent (0.3%) strongly disagree while nine (9) respondents who strongly disagree. This indicates that poverty has an intricate relationship with banditry/kidnapping.

Table 15: Illiteracy and Ignorance

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	129	36.9%
Disagree	18	5.1%
Strongly Agree	214	61.1%
Strongly Disagree	15	4.3%

Undecided	7	2%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

It was discovered from the respondents that illiteracy and ignorance are major contributory factors to the challenge of banditry in Nigeria. This is so because the data analysis shows that two hundred and fourteen respondents (214) representing sixty-one-point one percent (61.1%) strongly agree, one hundred and twenty-nine respondents (129) accounting for thirty-six-point nine percent (36.9%) agree, while those undecided are seven (7) or two percent (2%).

Research Question 4: *What are the challenges faced by Nigeria in implementing these security measures at the Nigeria-Niger border in Jibia border?*

Border challenges have affected Nigeria security negatively as illustrated in the data supplied by respondents. Table 16 shows that the majority of respondents representing fifty-point six percent (50.6%) or one hundred and seventy-seven (177) agree, forty-one-point seven percent (41.7 %) or one hundred and forty-six (146) strongly agree. Those who disagree and those who are undecided are tied at eleven (11) representing three-point one percent (3.1%) respectively, while one point four percent (1.4%) strongly disagrees.

Table 16: Nigeria's Border Challenges and Security

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	177	50.6%
Disagree	11	3.1%
Strongly Agree	146	41.7%
Strongly Disagree	5	1.4%
Undecided	11	3.1%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Table 17: Nigeria's Border Operatives and Temptation to Compromise in the Discharge of their Duties

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	109	31.1%
Disagree	10	2.9%
Strongly Agree	224	64.0%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Undecided	7	2%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

Data supplied by respondents to question four (4) on whether Nigeria's border operatives are under heavy temptation to compromise in the discharge of their duties due to enticement by bandits, provide a safe premise to conclude that Nigerian border operatives are under heavy pressure to compromise in their duties. Analysis of data supplied shows that one hundred and nine respondents (109) representing thirty-one-point one percent (31.1%) agreed, two hundred and twenty-four (224) respondents representing sixty-four percent (64%) strongly agree. Ten respondents (10) accounting for two-point nine percent (2.9%) disagree, seven (7) respondents or two percent (2%) were undecided while no respondent strongly disagree.

Table 18: Families of Victims

Options	Response	Percentage
Agree	208	56%
Disagree	6	1.7%
Strongly Agree	101	28.9%
Strongly Disagree	5	1.4%
Undecided	30	8.6%
Total	350	100%

Source: Field Survey, March 2023

On the proposition that addressed the question on whether or not the family of the victims of banditry are contributory factor to the crime of banditry because of the ransom being paid. From the data supplied by respondents sampled, majority of the opinion agree that the family of the victims of banditry is a contributory factor to the crime of banditry because of the ransom being paid. This is because two hundred and eight respondents (208) accounting for fifty-six percent (58%) which constitute the highest number agree with the proposition. The next highest number is among respondents who strongly agree with the assertion-one hundred and one respondents (101) or twenty-eight point nine (28.9%). Respondents who strongly disagree recorded the lowest number of five (5) or one point four percent (1.4%), while those who disagree are (6) or one point seven percent (1.7%) and those who were undecided stood at thirty (30) or eight-point six percent (8.6%) and thirteen (13) or three-point seven percent (3.7%).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The nature of banditry is assuming a dangerous trend. From the data supplied to the researcher by the respondents to the questions and interviews, it can be concluded that the nature of banditry is such that the victims experience threats from the traffickers. The victims interviewed were afraid and unwilling to give information. Trans-border crime has increased in the country because people are vulnerable due to their economic condition because majority of them are perceived to be from poor background.

Corroborating the proposition above, a report by Ojugbana (2015) on trans-border security shows that in 2014, 170, 100 arrived Nigeria through the land border. According to the report, the migrants had come from Mali (42, 323), Niger (34, 329), Cameroon (9,908) Gambia (8, 691), Somalia (5, 756) and some other nations (4,095). In the case of Nigeria, most of the immigrants were brought by syndicates to cause mayhem in the country.

In a similar view, Okpalakunne (2006) explained that banditry consists of both national and trans-national recruitment and movement of people for providing cheap, easy to manipulate and exploitable labour for domestic and agricultural work, commercial sex work or prostitution, begging, unregulated industrial work and street trading.

Banditry impacts negatively on Nigeria's Trans-border security. From the respondents' perspectives, banditry has impacted negatively on Nigeria's Trans-border security. The issues particular to banditry in its relation with other countries around the world is a threat to Nigeria's national security. For example, updated guidance for prosecutors on banditry produced by the Crown Prosecution Service (CPS) in May 2022 makes reference to the impact that bandits have on Nigeria trans-border security.

It was as a result of the menace of bandits in Nigeria and its increasing damage to the nation's trans-border security that some various security organizations were put up to stem the ugly tide. Among these organizations the most influential, powerful and well-

focused were the Nigeria Police Force, Nigeria Army, Nigeria Immigration and the Nigeria Customs (Njoku, 2005).

The strategies adopted by government to curb banditry in Nigeria are inadequate. The respondents are of the view that community and voluntary agencies have a clear role to play. They have the potential to act as effective mediators between trafficked people and statutory services.

Supporting the above position Blum (2014) asserts that however, in the current situation members of the public or community groups are unable to respond appropriately, unaware of referral pathways and uncertain of whether to refer people to untrusted statutory agencies and systems of support. Some agencies do valuable work here however funding and geographic reach may limit their current capacity. In the community at large, the first step is to raise awareness about referral pathways as well as the law on trafficking in the UK and to encourage debate and disclosure about instances of exploitation and abuse within the Nigerian community. Local authorities should appoint community liaison officers from the Nigerian community to lead training sessions as well as providing points of contact for anyone wishing to disclose trafficking experiences.

Again, Emeozor (2004) asserts that decision-making procedure is at the heart of the support system for victims of kidnapping and banditry. Its role is to define whether somebody has been a victim of the crime of banditry. This decision should be distinct from an immigration decision. A decision determines if somebody's past experiences fit the criteria of banditry. An asylum or immigration decision determines an individual's future risk and/or immigration status. The assessment as to whether somebody has been a victim of banditry should not be concerned with somebody's right to reside abroad; a victim should never be declined on the basis of immigration concerns. Similarly, it should be clear that a formal recognition that someone is or has been a victim of banditry does not give the man automatic right to remain abroad.

Corroborating the above points, Ando (2007) and (Chete, 2016) and Yukoshko (2009) inferred that banditry is a big problem for Nigeria's national security because a lot of people are being killed and man-hours are being wasted.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study holistically reviewed impact of banditry and interrogated its impact on emerging Trans-border security issues bedeviling Nigeria as well as how it has affected Nigeria's external image. The study contextualized banditry as a white-collar crime. There are a quite a number of existing literatures on the subject but with emphasis on the success and challenges of the institution put in place saddle with the responsibility of curbing the menace. These studies looked at the banditry and kidnapping from the perspective of challenges impeding effective security architecture and a knowledge demand that this research area exhibits. This research area drew the attention of the researcher because of escalation of the issue of banditry in Nigeria. This project gives an insight into the public assessment of the impact of banditry to Nigeria trans-border Security, historical evolution, development of banditry and government efforts in curbing banditry in Nigeria. Because of the sensitivity and hazard of the task involved, more men gender within the age bracket of 31–40 of age are mostly deployed to these security organization offices where data were obtained which are considered more capable of withstanding these hazards.

The academic qualification of respondents who supplied the data relating to the impact of banditry on Nigeria's trans-border Security are B.Sc. holders. Respondent answered questions like whether there is impact of banditry on Nigeria's Trans-Border Security. After analyzing their response, it is safe to conclude that banditry strongly impacted on the Nigeria trans-border Security. More so, the public opinion strongly shows that banditry have seriously contributed in denting external image of Nigeria. It is also the opinion of the respondent that the illegal migration of persons has adversely affected Trans-Border Security in Nigeria.

On the issue of whether Nigeria border operatives are under temptation to compromise in the discharge of their duties; majority of the respondent agree and strongly disagree that security operatives are under heavy pressure to compromise in the discharge of their duties, despite having a huge role to play in curbing insecurity in Nigeria. It was also gathered that, there is an agreement that a good means of livelihood is the reason for increased trans-border crime in Nigeria, while little percentage are yet to decide if that is true.

Respondent also hold different views on whether or not banditry is a threat to Nigeria's National Security, while some believed the assertion others opined that family factor are a contributory factors to the crime of banditry because of the ransoms being paid. Religious and traditional institutions are believed to have been used as a strategy and tools for campaign against banditry in Nigeria.

Similarly, respondent and adjudge relatively the security institutions to have assisted in ensuring that the country and the society at large put a stop to the banditry in Nigeria. It is also found that, the get-rich quick syndrome is one of the major challenges that causes banditry.

Conclusion

The study concluded that crime is a structural and collective attack against humanity, which has assumed a dangerous trend having its roots from the colonial times. Banditry in Nigeria is due to population boom and unfavorable economic conditions that aggravate unemployment, underemployment and insecurity, which prompt citizens to seek for better opportunities in other countries. These opportunities include education, decent jobs and higher income. Banditry remains a major challenge to the global community because it is a threat to human and the causes of crimes in the world at large.

The Public Enlightenment Unit of the various security institutions, with focus in remote areas of the northeast, northwest and north central are to partner with other NGOs on how to curb the menace of banditry in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proffered to mitigate the impact of banditry on Nigeria's Trans-Border Security.

- i. The nature of banditry has assumed a dangerous trend and this has made victims of not to even know where to access help and get protected. As such, protection for the victims of banditry must be structured so that victims can and will access it. Policy should acknowledge that state solutions are unlikely to deliver a full and effective response alone. Whether due to experiences in Nigeria or the threats to victims, people interviewed were afraid and unwilling to seek support from agencies such as the police.

- ii. The Federal government should come up with stiffer punishment for trans-border crimes especially banditry by enacting laws that pronounces stiffer jail terms for culprits of banditry.
- iii. The Federal and State Governments at the border areas to embark on the development and enlightenment of border communities by providing and improving infrastructural facilities such as school, hospital, electricity and portable pipes home water to all the borders community in the country.
- iv. In partnership with private organizations, the National Security Adviser should come up with an Inter-Agency Committee to Synergize efforts in checking trans-border crimes.
- v. The Federal government should sustain the Joint Patrol operations existing at the country's various borders with effective checkpoint to march with the increasing rate of trans-border crimes such as banditry.
- vi. The Federal Government should call for a review of the ECOWAS protocol on free movement and resident permits. This should be so because Nigeria National interest should supersede any regional agreement/commitment
- vii. The federal Government of Nigeria to re-organize the border security operational system to all security agencies in line in the international best practice by;
 - a) Commencing E-border security by providing modern digital equipment and CCTV Cameras at all the border control post to enable effective monitoring of the porous borders for efficient border security operations.
 - b) To provide enough patrol boats, vehicles and helicopters.
 - c) Increase the number of personnel in all the nation's borders.
 - d) To commence training of security agencies in modern borders security

References

- Abdullahi, A. (2019). Rural Banditry, Regional Security, And Integration in West Africa. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 2(3), 644-654.
- Adebayo, B. (2018). Nigeria overtakes India in extreme poverty ranking. The CNN. Retrieved from: <https://www.edition.cnn.com/nigeria-overtakes-india-in-extreme-pverty-ranking>.
- Adeniyi, T. (2015). Why incoming FCT Minister must act fast on cattle rustling. Daily Trust, July 1st. Retrieved from: www.dailytrust.com.ng/daily/index.php/city-news/58662-why-incoming-FCT-administration-must-act-fast-on-cattle-rustling.
- Akowe, T. & Kayode, B. (2014). Cattle rustling: A northern nightmare. The Nation, March 30th. Retrieved from: <http://thenationonlineng.net/cattle-rustling-northern-nightmare>
- Alabelewe, A. (2020). Bandits kill 10 in Friday, Saturday attacks on three Kaduna villages. The Nation, July 26th. Retrieved from: <https://thenationonlineng.net/bandits-kill-10-in-friday-saturday-attacks-on-three-kaduna-villages/>
- Alabelewe, A. (2020). Bandits kill seven, kidnap one in fresh attacks on Kaduna villages. The Nation, April 24th. Retrieved from: <https://thenationonlineng.net/bandits-kill-seven-kidnap-one-in-freshattacks-on-kaduna-villages/>

- Alao, D. O., Atere, C. O. & Alao, O. (2015). *Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria: The challenges and lessons*. In Alao, D (ed), *Issues in conflict, peace and Government*. Ibadan: Fodnab Ventures.
- Bashir, M. (2014). Hopes for an end to cattle theft. Daily Trust, September 4th. Retrieved from: www.dailytrust.com.ng/daily/feature/33468-hopes-for-an-end-to-cattle-theft.
- Kuna, M. J. & Jibrin. I. (eds.) (2016). *Rural banditry and conflicts in Northern Nigeria*, Abuja: Centre for Democracy and Development.
- Maureen, O. M. & Blessing, N. O. (2018). Insurgency and its implication on Nigeria economic growth. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 7(2), 492-501.
- Mustapha, U. N. (2019). Armed banditry and internal security in Zamfara State. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 10(8), 1219-1226.
- Okoli, A. C. & Ochim, F. (2016). Forestlands and national security in Nigeria: A threat-import Analysis. *IIARD International Journal of Political and Administrative Studies*, 2(2), 43- 53.
- Okoli, A. C. & Ogayi, C. O. (2018). Herdsmen militancy and humanitarian crisis in Nigeria: A Theoretical briefing. *African Security Review*, 27(2), 129-143.
- Okoli, A. C. & Okpaleke, F. N. (2014). Banditry and crisis of public safety in Nigeria: Issues in national security strategies. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(4), 350–62.
- Okoli, A. C. & Orinya, S. (2013). Oil pipeline vandalism and Nigeria"s national security. *Global Journal of Human Social Sciences*, XIII(v), 67-75.
- Okoli, A. C. & Ugwu, A. C. (2019). Of marauders and brigands: Scoping the threat of rural banditry in Nigeria's north west. *Brazilian Journal of African Studies*, 4(8), 201-222.
- Olaniyon, A. & Yahaya, A. (2016). Cows, bandits, and violent conflicts: Understanding cattle rustling in northern Nigeria. *Africa Spectrum*, 51(3), 93-105.
- Olaniyon, A. (2018). Foliage and violence: Interrogating forests as a security threat in Nigeria. *African Security Review*, 27(1), 1-20.
- Omede, A. J. (2011). Nigeria: Analysing the security challenges of the Goodluck Jonathan administration. *Canadian Social Science*, 7(5), 90-102.
- Orjinmo, N. (2020). *Kastina: The motorcycle bandits terrorising northwest Nigeria*. BBC News, July 5th. Retrieved from: BBC news: https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-53009704?intlink_from_url=&link_location=live-reporting-story
- Rufa'i, M. A. (2018). Cattle rustling and armed banditry along Nigeria-Niger borderlands. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 23(4), 66-73.
- Suleiman, A. O. (2017). Thematic Appraisal on the impulsive upsurge of yahoo-yahoo in the 21st Century in Nigeria: Qu'anic standpoint.
- Tauna, A. (2016). We have tamed cattle rustling, we will tame kidnapping–Northern governors. Daily Post, January 30th. Retrieved from: <http://dailypost.ng/2016/01/30/we-have-tamed-cattle-rustlingwewill-tackle-kidnapping-northern-governors>
- Yusuf, V. (2015). Deadly persistence of cattle rustling. Daily Trust, May 16th. Retrieved from: www.dailytrust.com.ng/weekly/index.php/features/20488-deadly-persistence-of-cattle-rustling